

Beyond One Million Genomes

M4.1 - Technology and ELSI compliance check

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Beyond One Million Genomes

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B1MG

1. Executive Summary

During the Beyond 1 Million Genomes project, a scoping paper defining the required functionalities which would enable secure cross-border data access was published. Based on this paper, a draft infrastructure to support this was refined for the rare disease use case. This PoC and associated user workflow, was presented to Beyond 1 Million Genomes (B1MG) WP2 and 1+ Million Genomes (1+MG) WG2 for feedback, which identified ELSI issues within the proposal. Based on this feedback, the PoC and use case was adjusted, including developments within the technologies proposed within the infrastructure, and these were incorporated into an updated PoC, which was subsequently developed within the Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) project as a Starter Kit. However, not all ELSI issues have been identified or, or even those identified addressed, so ongoing work is required to identify and address these issues. With the Starter Kit, which supports other use cases, a Data Protection by Design and Default process has been initiated, which we proposed to perform in a hybrid approach, both top down and bottom up, to ensure compliance with applicable laws and regulations.

2. Introduction

To support the ambition of the 1+ Million Genomes (1+MG) declaration, an infrastructure is required to allow the secure cross border access to genomic data. WP4 is tasked with proposing the technical infrastructure along with 1+MG WG5, while the ELSI and governance are part of 1+MG WG2 and B1MG WP2. To engage WP2 / WG2, as well as other 1+MG use cases (WGs 8 - 12) and working groups, a proposed proof of concept (PoC) was developed within WP4 to elicit technical, scientific, and ELSI (Ethical, Legal, and Societal Issue) feedback on the proposed infrastructure.

3. Functionalities and the proposed infrastructure

The original scoping paper¹ identified the five functionalities required of an infrastructure that supports secure cross border genomic data access - data discovery, data access management, storage and interfaces, data reception, and processing (data analysis). To provide these functionalities, an infrastructure was proposed based on state of the art tools, applications, and standards, such as those managed by the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health² (GA4GH) or the International Organization for Standardization³ (ISO).

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6089582>

² <https://www.ga4gh.org/>

³ <https://www.iso.org/home.html>

The rare disease use case was chosen as a demonstrator for the PoC, as they had experience in federated data access of genomic data, for example via the Solve-RD⁴ project, and based on this the initial set of tools and standards were chosen, as shown in Figure 1. The functionalities are listed across the top, supported by the applications and services detailed in the RD Use Case, which in turn are supported by the GA4GH standards at the bottom. In this use case two rare disease specific applications were used, the Genome Phenome Analysis Platform⁵ (GPAP) and MatchMaker Exchange⁶ (MME). GPAP supports the data analysis functionality by allowing a user to analyse both whole exome and whole genome data, while MME supports data discovery by allowing a user to search for datasets which include individuals with a similar phenotype and / or similar genotype.

The other applications, standards, and services were more generic and not specific to the rare disease use case, and include Beacon⁷, Federated EGA⁸, Resource Entitlement Management System⁹ (REMS), and the ELIXIR (now LifeScience) Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure^{10,11} (AAI). One of the main issues regarding the rare disease use case was linking phenotypic and genomic discovery queries, which was not supported by the Beacon version 1 at the time of the PoC. Hence the use of MME to support phenotypic discovery in the original PoC.

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41431-021-00859-0>

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.1002/humu.24353>

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.1002%2Fhumu.22858>

⁷ <https://github.com/ga4gh-beacon/beacon-v2>

⁸ <https://ega-archive.org/federated>

⁹ <https://github.com/CSCfi/remis/>

¹⁰ <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/compute/aai>

¹¹ <https://lifescience-ri.eu/lis-login/>

Figure 1: The original rare disease PoC.

This original PoC was demonstrated¹² to the different WGs and stakeholders, and feedback was received from WG2 (described below) as well as other WGs, which focussed mainly on the way the PoC was specific to the rare disease use case. To address this, an updated PoC was developed with the cancer use case, which also aimed to be more generic and applicable to the other use cases.

The update PoC was able to take advantage of the Beacon version 2¹³ standard, as it had been approved by GA4GH. This standard allowed Beacon queries that linked phenotypic, disease, and genomic queries, so MME was no longer required for this functionality. This also meant the user journey could be modified to comply with the requirements from WG2 (Figure 2).

¹² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6MtIJA4xDU>

¹³ <https://doi.org/10.1002/humu.24369>

Figure 2. The updated PoC with the user journey for 2 actors added, based on feedback from WG2. There is no MME or GPAP, with the discovery functionality solely provided by Beacon V2, and the processing (data analysis) now a generic use case specific pipeline.

4. Identified Issues with the original PoC

The PoC was developed in parallel with the work of WP2 in B1MG, so was not expected to achieve compliance with all ELSI when developed. It leveraged existing standards and technologies within the PoC to enable the discussions on the technical, scientific, and ELSI requirements to proceed. Examples of issues identified were:

- the use of a virtual cohort to ensure the data minimisation principle was met,
- a single data access request to the virtual cohort and no inter-node discovery process,
- the use of registered access whenever personal data was processed even if the result of these operations was pseudonymised or anonymised,
- the different expected workflows for primary or secondary use of these data,
- and the way the location of the personal data was identified during the PoC workflow.

The use of a virtual cohort is being addressed, and a technical proposal on how to support it using both the User Portal and REMS is being created within the Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) project.

The issue with processing of personal data at anonymous level was identified via the original Beacon query, where a discovery action was performed using an implementation of the original version 1 Beacon. In this case, only aggregate data was

loaded to the Beacon, so was not personal data, but for the updated Beacon version 2 which would allow more specific queries, it would be expected that individual data would be loaded, hence the requirement for a user to register and accept a set of terms and conditions prior to performing the Beacon query. However there is still ongoing work to ensure that these discovery queries are ELSI compliant across the whole infrastructure.

The location of the data in the PoC was identified during the workflow to demonstrate cross border data access in a federated context, but need not be part of the updated workflow within GDI especially as use of a virtual cohort is being worked on, the user can be abstracted away from the specific location of the data they have access to. The GDI Starter Kit demonstrated federated computation, both with containers and GA4GH standard compliant workflows, which could be run on a range of compute by a user without the user knowing the location of either the data or the SPE that performed the analysis.

For the primary use of data, there would be expected to be an expedited workflow without the application to a DAC for access, and this case has not been specifically modelled here, however this will need to be investigated, especially with the development of EHDS and linking the genomic and health data to maximise utility of these data.

The GDI Starter Kit has also helped identify issues within the technologies among GDI partners, such as the requirement to know the level of assurance (LoA) that an Identity Provider (IdP) has for a particular user before they can access a resource.

5. Updated PoC (GDI Starter Kit)

The B1MG PoC was updated within the GDI project to become more generic, and support multiple different workflows, as well as demonstrate how different implementations of products that support one or more of the five functionalities could be utilised within the Starter Kit to help conform to national requirements or priorities. As standards were used to connect the functionalities, or products, together, the product itself could be changed, as well as the workflow or user journey. This helps to ensure that the proposed infrastructure can adapt to changes in the ELSI that apply to it, as new laws come into practice or existing laws are updated.

6. Next steps

Continued ELSI work is needed on the infrastructure to ensure it meets the 1+MG framework and relevant best practice, laws, and regulations across all member states within 1+MG. This has been planned with workshops between WGs 2, 3, and 5 within 1+MG to clarify the requirements on the data and user journeys.

Currently the individual products of the GDI Starter Kit are being technically analysed to ensure they conform to the data protection principles¹⁴ within the General Data Protection Regulation¹⁵ (GDPR), and these principles are being taken into account as the

¹⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679&from=EN#d1e1807-1-1>

¹⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>

standard operating procedures (SOPs), processes, and workflows are being designed within the GDI.

The User Portal is being modelled and requirements analysis is being carried out, to ensure it provides the necessary discovery and data access functionality while conforming to the applicable ELSI, including the transfer of both non-personal and personal metadata related to the special category data within the GDI infrastructure. Work is ongoing on the data access workflow, utilising a single point of data application for only those data needed (virtual cohort) for the specified research question. Outreach is planned within GDI to prospective nodes, and this engagement is identifying more issues for particular national use cases, such as the LoA issue with the LifeScience AAI mentioned above. This is partly due to increased involvement of technical specialists from each node as GDI ramps up, and this knowledge can be leveraged via GDI Pillar II workshops, and node feedback and report, to help drive the development of the infrastructure. Additionally this feedback will be communicated outside the GDI where necessary, for example to GA4GH or other standard setting organisations, as well as other associated data spaces and infrastructures where necessary.

7. Conclusions

The feedback from WG2, which has been incorporated into the updated PoC and now the GDI Starter Kit is the first stage in the Technical and ELSI compliance check, and demonstrates how complex, both technically and legally, providing cross border data access within the 1+MG framework is. The increase in interested participants, due to GDI, has expanded the number of experts, especially at a technical level, reviewing the infrastructure for their national use cases and this in turn is continuing to help develop the infrastructure and ensure that it meets the diverse range of ELSI that exist within the GDI partners.

